

Entanglement protocol in a generalized quantum network with $|W\rangle$ states

Mateo Blanco Rodríguez

atlanTTic, I&C Lab
Universidad de Vigo
Vigo, Spain
mblanco@det.uvigo.es*

The field of quantum communications has developed significantly in recent years, both theoretically and experimentally. Several protocols have emerged, allowing secure communications between n -parties, and devices capable of implementing them are becoming increasingly common. Foundational protocols, such as BB84 and COW4, have been achieved and are commercially available, but the ultimate goal remains the creation of a global quantum network.

We propose a layered architecture for a quantum network [1], where a Central Controller manages all network resources and allocations. This controller connects to several clusters with quantum switches deployed in arbitrary topologies to meet the network's needs. The quantum switches are arranged in a star formation, each connecting to several individual nodes. This setup is simulated in NetSquid [2].

Our proposed entanglement distribution scheme is based on $|W\rangle$ states in atom-photon systems. Each switch can create several such trios and manage communications. Each node is equipped with an atom capable of absorbing one of the photons. The process, assuming node A , n_A , in switch A , Sw_A , and node B , n_B , in switch B , Sw_B , wish to communicate, is as follows: a $|W\rangle$ state is generated in each switch, with one photon sent to each respective node, and entanglement measurements performed, resulting in two Bell pairs on each side. The other photon is sent through the network, acting as a virtual switch, and the Bell measurement on photon A and B results in shared entanglement between Sw_A and Sw_B . Finally, the remaining photons in the nodes swap entanglement with the switches, achieving end-to-end entanglement between n_A and n_B .

Although this method involves more steps than the regular entanglement swapping proposed for general network architectures, it allows for longer decoherence times [3]. This enables more rounds of purification, achieving more stable communications and better ensuring successful pairing between users. It can trivially extend to n -parties with generalized entanglement measurements for the flying photons.

References

- [1] B. He, D. Zhang, S. W. Loke, S. Lin, and L. Lu, "Building a hierarchical architecture and communication model for the quantum internet," 2024.
- [2] T. Coopmans *et al.*, "Netsquid, a network simulator for quantum information using discrete events," *Communications Physics*, vol. 4(1), 2021.
- [3] M. H. Abobeih *et al.*, "One-second coherence for a single electron spin coupled to a multi-qubit nuclear-spin environment," *Nature Comm.*, vol. 9(1), 2018.

*This work has been supported by project QURSA, under grants TED2021-130369B-C31, TED2021-130369BC32, TED2021-130369B-C33 funded by MCIN/AEI/10.13039/501100011033 and by the "European Union NextGenerationEU/PRTR". The work is also funded by the Plan Complementario de Comunicaciones Cuánticas, Spanish Ministry of Science and Innovation (MICINN), Plan de Recuperación NextGenerationEU de la Unión Europea (PRTR-C17.11, CITIC Ref. 305.2022), and Regional Government of Galicia (Agencia Gallega de Innovación, GAIN, CITIC Ref. 306.2022). Additionally, this work has also received financial support from Consellería de Educación, Ciencia, Universidades e Formación Profesional and co-funded by UE.